

Enabling Decarbonization with a Coordinated Gas-Electricity System

Abstract

Immediate action must be taken to reduce carbon emissions in the energy sector to meet net-zero targets. While many studies focus on decarbonization through electrification, using the existing gas network to help decarbonize can have numerous advantages. In this study we build a sector coupled PyPSA model of Vancouver Island to investigate decarbonization efforts through linking the electrical and gas networks. use of hydrogen as a fuel source is explored. We find that with increasing electrical demand, the island will quickly be unable to meet its own load. Introducing CCHPs and blending large amounts of hydrogen into the natural gas supply will result in a cheaper, less emitting, and more independent system. However, this does come at the cost of needing to install new facilities to generate clean hydrogen.

Terminology

Nomenclature

$b \in B = \{0, \dots B - 1\}$	Label of buses
$t \in T = \{0, \dots T - 1\}$	Label of snapshots
p	Modelled load
a	Actual load
n	Simulated load from NREL
w	Weighting factor
h	Hydrogen blend amount
g	Power generation
V	Volume conversion

Subscripts

e	Energy load (electricity + heating + cooling)
elc	Electricity load
$heat$	Heat load
$cool$	Cooling load
res	Residential load
com	Commercial load
ind	Industrial load
l	Lower hydrogen blend amount
u	Upper hydrogen blend amount
ng	Natural Gas
$h2$	Hydrogen

Introduction

Achieving 2050 net-zero emission targets, which most countries have committed to at the 26th United Nations Climate Change Conference of the Parties [1], requires diligent planning and policy development strategies. Therefore, understanding the technological requirements and economic impacts of different transition pathways needs to be studied. Modelling of the electricity system allows researchers, planners, and policy makers to identify key requirements for long-term decarbonization success. However, the flow of energy is larger than just that of the electric system, with specifically the gas network being closely linked to it. Energy models that co-optimize both gas and electricity networks can offer new insight into where to focus decarbonization efforts.

Electricity system models for long-term decarbonization analysis have found that variable renewable energy capacity, such as wind and solar, will see significant build out in the coming years. Studies such as those done by Jayadev et al. [2] and Motalebi et al. [3] show that for the United States and Canada to decarbonize their electricity sector by 2050, at least 40% of the generation mix will be from variable renewables. They also note that complete decarbonization will be prohibitively expensive when compared to the costs associated with only reaching 80% decarbonization by 2050. The cost increase is largely attributed to the elimination of low carbon and cheap fossil fuel generation facilities, and the addition of large batteries for grid stability. This result is supported by Mahone et al. [4] who compare the results of two decarbonization models for the US Northeast and California. They summarized that both studies predict a large expansion into variable renewables, and that electrification loads will increase quickly due to the transportation and heating sectors moving towards electrical solutions. Moreover, Mahone et al. note that increased grid-edge innovation and distribution improvements are needed to account for the increased electrification load. Both studies are hinting or directly stating the same results; to remain cost feasible, decarbonization efforts need to go beyond just electrifying everything in the system.

These studies highlight two important points; the importance of creating a stable system that incorporates large shares of variable renewable energy, and that innovation is required to manage increasing electrification in a cost-effective manner. Coupling the electricity and gas networks can aid in addressing these concerns by distributing the load through a diverse portfolio of energy generation technologies. Furthermore, studies such as those done by Brown et al. [5] and Evangelopoulou et al. [6] explore how emerging technologies, such as using hydrogen as an energy carrier, can contribute to cost-effective decarbonization pathways. Specifically, these studies reveal that systems which incorporate hydrogen will see emission reductions, and if hydrogen reaches wide scale adoption, can see system level cost reductions.

To quantify the benefits of coupling the electricity and gas networks, energy system modelling is employed. Our study develops an energy system model for Vancouver Island to measure the emission and operational cost benefits of integrating these two networks.

Literature Review

Resource allocation and investment strategies can be greatly improved through integrating multiple energy sectors into one modelling study, with the benefits being well documented [7]–[9]. Linking the electrical and gas network requires the implementation of so-called sector coupling technologies. These technologies will convert one energy carrier to another, such as how a furnace will transform natural gas

into heat energy. While a wide array of sector coupling technologies exist, combined cooling, heat, and power systems, and power-to-gas systems will be the focus of our literature review.

To properly evaluate the impacts of integrated networks with variable renewables, selecting or building a model that accounts for the specific conditions of the system is imperative. Bottom-up engineering models are a suitable choice for evaluating technology transitions [10], however, scaling these models for detailed analysis can quickly deteriorate if large amounts of unaggregated data are added. Further exacerbating this issue is the need to capture short-term temporal variability in the electricity system with variable renewable energy resources, such as wind and solar. As Bistline et al. [11] note in their review of energy system modelling challenges, capturing the daily and seasonal production limitations from variable renewable energy generation facilities is necessary to properly evaluate their contribution. If the temporal resolution is lowered (coarser time steps), the reliance on variable sources may be overstated. Therefore, performing operational feasibility testing at high temporal resolutions (hourly time steps or less) are required to properly evaluate a proposed system, with Quirion and Shrizadeh [12] specifically comparing aggregation methods for long term sector-coupled models. The authors show that capturing the uniqueness of each day at lower temporal resolution is more effective compared to using representative days which will average time-dependent values. Ensuring the correct time slicing structure is selected will be necessary to obtain credible results.

An increasingly discussed technology to couple the electrical and gas networks are combined cooling, heat, and power (CCHP) systems. CCHP systems use a gas power generation unit to produce electricity, while the waste heat is used to meet heating loads and/or cooling demands through an absorption chiller. Gu et al. [15] completed a review of current research focusing on CCHP systems in micro-grids and highlight the research fields acceptance of CCHP systems to help mitigate energy-related problems through sector coupling. However, they caution that more operational data is needed to dynamically model these systems at high-temporal resolution and further research on demand response strategies is needed. Studies that focus solely on optimizing CCHP performance, such as those does by Wegener et al. [16] or Soheyli et al. [17] support these findings and note that effect demand response strategies can maximize profits through accounting for price fluctuations in the electricity and gas markets.

Power-to-gas (P2G) technologies allow electrical energy to be converted into gas energy, with our study specifically looking at hydrogen P2G system as this is an increasingly discussed topic [5], [13], [14]. Hydrogen P2G systems use electric energy to power electrolyzers which split water into hydrogen and oxygen gas. The hydrogen can then be blended into the natural gas pipelines, used as a fuel source for other technologies such as for hydrogen fuel cells, or stored for other use. As Brown et al. [5] note in their study of a zero emission European system, P2G can be especially impactful in networks with large shares of variable renewables. Due to the flexibility gas pipelines provide in storing energy, managing periods of low production from variable renewable becomes easier. Nastasi et al. [13] explore the concept of linking a hydrogen P2G systems to a series of solar arrays on a small island to manage periods of minimal production. Their findings highlight the robustness of hydrogen as an energy carrier and note its comparable infrastructure operating costs to current energy systems. Maroufmashat et al. [14] expand on P2G system benefits and study different policy pathways for the technology. They support the points of Nastasi et al. [13] and further highlight the economical importance of utilizing the existing natural gas network to meet end use demand. They conclude by suggesting P2G systems are an ideal technology to manage the decarbonization transition and should be phased into the system as soon as technologically feasible.

Within the literature, there is a gap that brings together the detailed modelling of CCHP systems with larger scale energy system models to evaluate the potential benefits CCHP systems have on the entire system. Furthermore, investigating how hydrogen blends affect both a detailed operational model of a CCHP system, and in turn the full-scale energy system model, has yet to be done. The closest work found was that done by Li et al. [18] who investigated how wind energy, hydrogen P2G technology, and CCHP systems can work together to recover curtailed energy. They show that if sized correctly, significant amounts of hydrogen can be generated while also lowering system costs and emissions. However, Li et al. stop short of creating a full system model. Other similar work is done by Brown et al. [5] who create a European energy system model that incorporates both hydrogen and combined heating and power systems, (not CCHP). However, their study does not link to a detailed optimization model of a CCHP system.

Our research intends to fill this literature gap by proposing a methodology to link a detailed CCHP system model to an energy system model with a sub-hourly time resolution. This will combine system level energy modelling research with detailed CCHP modelling research to study the potential benefits of integrating CCHP system into the wider energy system. Moreover, this study will also include how hydrogen blending into the natural gas network can work with this system and what emission reduction potentials it can offer.

Methods

This section describes the modelling framework used and provides justification on its applicability for this study. Following this, a description of all data sources and data assumptions is discussed.

Modelling Framework

Existing literature demonstrates two main approaches to develop a sector coupled energy model; create a custom model that ties multiple concepts from different studies together or build off an existing modelling framework that supports sector coupling. While custom models can help answer very specific questions, selecting an existing framework and modifying it through the addition of new constraints is suitable for our needs. We use the Python for Power System Analysis (PyPSA) [19] framework which is a reputable framework and has been used for numerous case studies on sector coupling [5], [20], [21].

PyPSA is an open-source modelling framework for power system simulations and optimization studies. Functionality includes both non-linear and linear power flow simulations, and linear power flow cost optimization. The linear cost optimization module is employed in our study and will solve for optimal system operating cost based on technical and economic constraints and parameters. The optimization module supports open-source solvers, such as GLPK or CBC, and commercial solvers, such as CPLEX or Gurobi.

User configurability is at the core of PyPSA framework. High level modelling decisions, such as the spatial resolution, temporal resolution, and energy carriers is determined by the modeler. Detailed modelling components, such as generation stations, loads, transmission lines, transformers, and storage facilities are configured by the user on a unit-by-unit level. Support for both time-varying generation and load profiles are native to the framework, situating PyPSA to work with variable renewable energy systems easily. Furthermore, the user can control unit dispatch and capacity expansion parameters on individual generators, storage units, transmission lines, and transformers.

System Representation

Our representative system consists of two main interconnected networks, an electrical network and a gas network. These networks are used to transfer energy between different nodes (called buses) to meet user defined demands. This section will describe these two networks, discuss how they are connected, and explain how the heating and cooling system are incorporated into the model.

Electrical Network

Figure 1 shows a schematic of the electricity system configuration. The base building component in PyPSA is a geospatially located bus to which all other components connect. Each bus has a single energy carrier, electricity in this case. Energy enters the model through generators which operate on any user defined energy carrier, such as water or wind. Energy leaves the model through exogenously defined loads, or efficiency losses associated with each component. Line connections and transformers are bi-directional and connect two buses to create energy flow paths. Lines connect buses at the same voltage level, while transformers connect buses at different voltage levels. Each bus can have as many connections to other components or loads as the modeller needs.

Figure 1: Electricity System Representation (Adapted from [19])

Gas Network

Figure 2 shows a schematic of the gas network configuration. Much like the electrical network, there are buses to which loads, and bidirectional links (which represent pipelines) can connect. Furthermore, each bus also has a storage unit which is used to maintain pressure at each bus. This provides the system flexibility to store gas, as there are minimum and maximum operating pressures on the network. Losses in the gas network are not considered, meaning compressors to maintain pressure are not included.

Figure 2: Gas Network Representation (Adapted from [19])

Sector Coupling

Figure 3 shows how the electrical and gas networks interconnect. Due to the gas network being heavily relied on to meet heat loads, tracking heating and cooling potential from the system is needed. Therefore, heating and cooling buses with associated loads are added. Figure 3 shows how sector coupling technologies are used to connect buses of different energy carriers, however, this is an example only and the specific technologies and commodities used in our model are later discussed.

Figure 3: Integrated Network Representation (Adapted from [19])

Sector coupling technologies (such as air conditioners) connect two buses and allow the conversion of one energy carrier into another. Moreover, sector coupling technologies can often generate more than one type of energy; such as heat pumps meeting heating or cooling loads, or combined heat and power systems (CHP) meeting heat and electricity loads. Also of note are how traditional large scale natural gas turbines are represented by a sector coupling technology. Unlike the gas generator shown in Figure 1, the gas used by the generator now needs to be taken from the shared gas network.

Finally, all loads in Figure 3 are shifted off the gas network and have been replaced by loads on the heating and cooling buses. This study is to investigate how best to allocate resources, including the consumption

of gas. By defining loads on the heating and cooling busses, we can study what sector coupling technologies should be prioritized to meet end use demand.

Spatial Resolution

Vancouver Island is a medium sized island (roughly $31,000 \text{ km}^2$) located off the West coast of British Columbia, Canada. It is used as a case study in this project for two main reasons; firstly, it can be modelled almost as an independent region, with only three electrical lines and one natural gas pipeline connecting it to mainland British Columbia. This helps in reducing uncertainty around modelling transmission systems. Secondly, we are very familiar with the current Vancouver Island energy system and have contacts who can help find data.

The electrical network on Vancouver Island is operated by BC Hydro and consists of both transmission lines (60kV to 500kV) and distribution lines ($< 60\text{kV}$). In this study, we only consider the transmission network to ensure the model remains computationally tractable. Geographic Information System (GIS) data is collected from the Integrated Cadastral Information Society [22], a membership based society that facilitates the sharing of spatial data for different governments and utilities in British Columbia. The raw GIS electrical transmission line data and PyPSA processed transmission line data for Vancouver Island are shown in Figure 4a and Figure 4b respectively.

Figure 4: Electricity Transmission System Represented in (a) GIS data (b) PyPSA

The PyPSA representation shows all transmission connections as straight-line segments connected at substations. Each substation represents a bus (as shown in Figure 1) and each line has metadata associated with it, such as the line length, and voltage. Power limits are not associated with the GIS data, and are therefore approximated based on their voltage from [23]. Transformer information is also not included in the GIS data and is instead pulled from BC Hydro's Operating Order 5T-14 at [24]. In instances where buses at different voltage levels exist at the same geospatial location, generators are attached to the highest voltage level bus, while loads are attached to the lowest voltage level bus. All transmission lines and transformers are allowed to expand capacity, however, there is a prohibitively high capital cost associated with expansion. This ensures the model will only invest in new infrastructure as a last resort.

The gas network on Vancouver Island is operated by FortisBC and, while large, does not fully cover the island. Figure 5a shows GIS data on the gas transmission network, sourced via The Integrated Cadastral Information Society [22], while Figure 5b shows the PyPSA processed gas line data for Vancouver Island.

Figure 5: Gas System Represented in (a) GIS data (b) PyPSA

The metadata associated with the transmission level gas GIS data does not have clear bus location (such as substations associated with the electrical network), Therefore, the gas network is overlaid on the electrical network. If a gas line passes near an electrical bus, a new gas bus is created at that geospatial location. While this results in a gas system that is slightly shifted from reality, this approximation will have minimal effect on system results. Finally, all gas enters the modelled system through a dummy generator, shown by the line leaving the island in Figure 5a. The amount of energy delivered by this pipeline is not openly available information, therefore the size is approximated through the use of average national natural gas usage rates supplied by the Government of Canada at [25].

The key infrastructure statistics for all networks are shown in Table 1 below. The number of buses on electricity network only represent buses at load centers, not auxiliary buses that are used to tap into transmission lines. In addition to the electrical and gas network, each geospatial location where a load is placed also has a heating and cooling bus (see Figure 3). These buses are not connected as no district heating or cooling is considered.

Table 1: System Network Representation Key Statistics

Network	Voltage Level (kV)	Number Buses	Number Lines
Electricity	69	13	16
Electricity	138	57	122
Electricity	230	12	19
Electricity	500	2	1
Gas	-	38	52
Heating	-	70	-
Cooling	-	70	-

Temporal Resolution

Systems with prominent shares of variable renewable energy require high temporal resolutions to capture intermittency effects of generation [11]. Due to data limitations on demand and renewable generation profiles, 15 minute time intervals are the finest time steps that can be used. However, given the geographical scope of this project, 15min is reasonable to remain computationally tractable over varying model horizons. Furthermore, due to the data source used for demand profiles (later discussed) the time horizon is limited to the 2018 year.

We choose not to perform any temporal aggregation, and instead run the model consecutively over a series of days. If clustering methods are used to select representative days, we re ensures we can reduce the chance our model will average out events that can strain the system, such as periods with high demand and low generation from variable renewables. The downside of not aggregating is that we restrict how many days we can run due to computation limits.

Technologies and Commodities

Vancouver Island has an array of energy generation sources, with a few hydroelectric dams and a single combined cycle natural gas generation facility contributing to the bulk of the installed capacity. There are smaller hydroelectric dams and biomass facilities providing dispatchable generation capacity scattered across the island. Variable generation sources include one wind farm located at the north of the island, and many run-of-river stations installed throughout the system. Figure 6a shows the installed capacity by energy carrier, with Figure 6b showing the spatial breakdown of the generators. The large generation capacity stations are taken from the Integrated Cadastral Information Society’s [22] dataset, with the smaller stations being taken from BC Hydro’s website [26] and BC Hydro’s list of independent power producers [27].

Figure 6: Generation Capacity on Vancouver Island by (a) Type (b) Geographic Location

It should be noted that no solar energy generation is included in this study. Utility scale solar capacity is not currently installed on the island, and with our study focusing on the transmission system, we are not considering residential rooftop solar resources. The next section will further elaborate on renewable generation potential on the island.

All generation capacity shown in Figure 6 is used to generate electricity, however, sector coupling capacity also needs to be considered. Four sector coupling technologies are added to the system; furnaces, heat pumps, air conditioners, and combined cooling, heat, and power systems (CCHP). How these technologies connect between energy carriers is summarized in Table 2. Boilers are not considered in this study as they are a unique sector coupling which can also act as a storage medium which comes with its own set of modelling challenges [28], especially for larger scale studies. Finding data on installed capacity values for furnaces, air conditioners, and heat pumps is not feasible without making heavy assumptions. Therefore, the optimization will assume no installed capacity to start, and decide how much capacity of each sector coupling link to install.

Table 2: Sector Coupling Technology Connections

Technology	Input Energy Carrier	Output Energy Carrier
Furnace	Gas	Heat
Air Conditioner	Electricity	Cooling
Heat Pump	Electricity	Heat and Cooling
CCHP	Gas	Electricity, Heat and Cooling

Each generation technology and sector coupling link have several parameters associated with them, such as costs and efficiencies. We will summarize our collected sources here, while our model will hold the actual values. Marginal costs for all utility scale electricity generation facilities are taken from the 2021 NREL Annual Technology Baseline (ATB) report [29], which provides both variable costs and fuel costs. Moreover, capacity factors for non-variable sources (such as natural gas stations) are also taken from the NREL ATB. Efficiencies for each station are taken from the assumptions document associated with the ATB dataset [29]. Costs and efficiencies (or the coefficient of performance) for sector coupling technologies are estimated based on national averages, as quite a range of values are seen. However, the general trend we ensured the model captured are the capital costs of heat pumps being more expensive than buying only a furnace or only an air conditioner. Finally, heat pumps are assumed to have efficiencies that do not change with temperature.

The parameters associated with the import of electricity and gas are handled differently than on-island generation stations. We are investigating the impact the existing gas network can have on the future energy system, therefore, we want to ensure the model does not resort to simply importing large amounts of electricity from the mainland. However, we also do not want to completely isolate the island from the mainland as the infrastructure is already built and would otherwise be a stranded asset. To model this, we apply a gas import rate of $\frac{\$1}{GJ}$, based on Fortis BC's rate to transport natural gas [30], and apply a very high cost associated with importing electricity. This will tell the model to only import electricity if all other options are unreasonably expensive or if the gas network has no additional capacity.

Finally, emission factors for each fuel are taken from the United States Environmental Protection Agency at [31]. The carbon dioxide, nitrous oxide, and methane from each fuel are converted into a carbon dioxide equivalent value and applied to the relevant fuels. This allows for tracking of system level emissions and provides us a means to apply a carbon tax.

Renewable Generation Profiles

Run-of-river generators and wind farms are the two primary variable power sources on Vancouver Island. Both plant types have daily and seasonal fluctuations, which must be taken into consideration. Additionally, developing a workflow that is flexible enough to accommodate solar integration is necessary if solar adoption is to be investigated in future studies. This section will explain the process used to create each of these profiles.

Data Handling

To help process and handle weather and hydrograph datasets, the Atlite Python Package is used [32]. Atlite provides a Python based API to assist in converting weather data into tabulated data useable by energy system models. Atlite assists in creating a raster (a matrix of geospatial cells) for a specific

geographic scope, aggregating data, and assigning generation profiles to specific stations based on user parameters.

Wind and Solar Data

The European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF) openly publishes a variety of weather datasets that researchers can use in studies. The ERA5 dataset [33] provides global weather data on a resolution of up to $30km \times 30km$ grids for every hour of the year, from 1959 to 2022. The data provided in ERA5 is based on historical observations and various weather modelling techniques, with the dataset providing full details on its methods. Figure 7 shows the gridded raster, average 100m wind speed, and irradiance levels for Vancouver Island in 2018. This data is given for every hour; however, our models temporal resolution is $15min$. Since no other openly available datasets are available at finer resolutions, the $15min$ datapoints are linearly interpolated from the hourly data.

Figure 7: Vancouver Island 2018 Wind and Solar Data

While Figure 7 shows average generation profiles, geolocating each generation station is required to get specific data. The capacity factor for each grid in the raster is first computed, then each generation station is located on the grid to calculate its generation potential for each timestep. This is shown in Figure 8a and Figure 8b respectively, with the resulting generation profile for the Cape Scott Wind Farm shown in Figure 9. To calculate the capacity factor, general information about the wind turbines operating conditions is required. In reality, the Cape Scott Wind Farm is made up of Vestas $V100$ $1.8MW$ wind turbines, however, this is not a currently supported Atlite wind turbine type. Instead, the wind turbines are assumed to be Vestas $V112$ $3MW$.

Figure 8: (a) Vancouver Island Wind Capacity Factor and (b) Geolocated Wind Generators

Figure 9: Cape Scott 2018 Generation Profile

Run-of-River Data

Tracking the geographic flow of water in the model is important, as it helps understand the generation potential for each cascading run-or-river and hydroelectric plant. The ERA5 dataset [33] provides surface runoff values (water that does not absorb into the soil), however, it does not provide data on the flow of rivers. Instead, the HydroBASINS dataset [34], [35] is used. HydroBASINS provide geospatial information on the connections of rivers and hydro basins. Pairing the surface runoff data with the HydroBASINS data in Atlite allows us to calculate the inflow for each generator by aggregating over catchment basins. The height map (used to help calculate surface runoff) and capacity distribution of the run-of-river plants throughout the island are show in Figure 10a and Figure 10b respectively.

(a) (b)

Figure 10: (a) Height Map and (b) Run-of-River Geolocated Generators

Unlike the wind turbine example, determining the time-varying capacity factor for each run of river plant is difficult without knowing the exact geography and installed turbines at each station. Without this information, the minimum and maximum operational flow rates is unknown, therefore, an assumption is made on its operational bounds. Specifically, if the flowrate deviates from the yearly average flow rate by more than 50%, it is assumed that the station has either reached its maximum generation potential or does not have enough flow to generate electricity. Obtaining better data on run-of-river plants is discussed in the future work section. The system aggregated run-of-river generation potential is shown in Figure 11.

Figure 11: Aggregated 2018 Run-of-River Generation Profile

Demand

As discussed in the System Representation section, three different end-use demands are included in the model at 15min resolution; those being electrical, heating, and cooling loads. These load types are further broken down into residential, commercial, and industrial loads. Furthermore, a separate electrical load for light-duty vehicle demand is added. This results in 10 different load types for each geospatial location. This section will describe how each of these loads is obtained and processed.

Sector Demand Data Source

Vancouver Island is part of BC Hydro's jurisdiction, however, BC Hydro does not release unaggregated electrical load data to the public. The closest openly available dataset is hourly resolution load for whole system found at [36], which is insufficient for this study. Moreover, FortisBC does not supply gas usage data (which could be used to estimate heating load). Therefore, another source is needed to estimate load on the island.

The National Renewable Energy Laboratory (NREL) in the United States, through the Open Energy Data Initiative, published an end-use load profiles dataset for residential and commercial buildings at [37]. This dataset provides 15min resolution data for electrical, heating, and cooling loads for a variety of building types, while considering the varying climate regions within the United States. The data is generated using physics-based building models, with all data being calibrated and validated for 2018 (see [38] for full details on their methodology). While the data presented by the NREL is United States specific, it can be used to approximate load profiles for Canada if the region has a similar climate zone. With Vancouver Island being adjacent to the United States border, the ASHRAE zone representing the North-West coast of the United States (Mixed – Marine Zone 4C) is assumed to be similar enough to Vancouver Islands climate zone.

Residential Loads

NREL's data provides residential loads at a per dwelling level, such as heat load per single-family detached home, or electrical load per apartment. To map this data to each PyPSA bus, Canadian census data from [39] provides numbers on how many of each dwelling type exist within census division areas. This can be used to calculate the residential load for each load type (electrical, heating, cooling) for each census division. Since no census was completed in 2018, the population changes between 2016 and 2021 data are assumed to be linear to estimate population in 2018.

Next, the geolocated boundaries of each census division are used to find the number of load buses within each subdivision. If only one bus exists within the division, the residential load is assigned to that bus. If multiple buses exist within the division, the load is evenly distributed. If no bus exists within the division, the load is assigned to the closest bus to the centroid of the division. This process is described by the flowchart in Figure 12. The resulting system level residential electrical, heating, and cooling loads are shown in

Figure 13.

Figure 12: Logic to Calculate Residential Loads

Figure 13: System Level Residential Load

Commercial Loads

Unlike the NREL residential data, which is provided at a per dwelling level, the commercial building loads are provided at a per ft^2 level. This is problematic as no openly available datasets are available that list the amount of commercial area, or number of commercial buildings, on Vancouver Island at any useful geographic scope. Therefore, a different method is needed to estimate commercial load.

The Canadian Energy Regulator at [40] provides breakdowns on total yearly end-use energy demand by sector (residential, commercial, and industrial) at a provincial level. From this the commercial load for each bus can be estimated through scaling the residential load following equation (1); where $p_{com,e}$ and $p_{res,e}$ represent our modelled commercial and residential energy loads, while $a_{com,e}$ and $a_{res,e}$ represent the actual energy yearly load taken from [40]. Note, these are total energy loads (electricity, heat, cooling) for the year.

$$\sum_t (p_{com,e})_{b,t} = \sum_t (p_{res,e})_{b,t} \cdot \left(\frac{a_{com,e}}{a_{res,e}} \right), \quad \forall_{b,t} \quad (1)$$

To distribute the yearly energy load ($p_{com,e}$) over all time steps, the building load profiles from the NREL dataset are used. Equation (2) is used to calculate a weighting factor, w , for each timestep; where the NREL energy load (n_e) is divided by the total yearly NREL energy load to represent the decimal percentage that timestep contributes to the yearly load.

$$w_t = \frac{(n_e)_t}{\sum_t (n_e)_t}, \quad \forall_t \quad (2)$$

Once a weighting factor for each timestep is calculated, equation (3) is applied to calculate the commercial energy load at each bus for each time slice ($p_{com,e}$). This equation guarantees that our total energy consumption follows the relationship obtained from [40]. However, it does not describe how much each sector (electricity, heating, and cooling) contributes to the total energy demand per time slice.

$$(p_{com,e})_{t,b} = (p_{com,e})_b \times w_t, \quad \forall_{t,b} \quad (3)$$

To determine each sectors contribution to meeting total energy demand per time slice, we calculate the ratio based on the original NREL dataset. The electrical, heating, and cooling demands can then be calculated following equations (4) – (6). Through applying this process, equation (7) will be guaranteed.

$$(p_{com,elc})_{t,b} = (p_{com,e})_{t,b} \times \frac{(n_{elc})_t}{(n_e)_t}, \quad \forall_{t,b} \quad (4)$$

$$(p_{com,heat})_{t,b} = (p_{com,e})_{t,b} \times \frac{(n_{heat})_t}{(n_e)_t}, \quad \forall_{t,b} \quad (5)$$

$$(p_{com,cool})_{t,b} = (p_{com,e})_{t,b} \times \frac{(n_{cool})_t}{(n_e)_t}, \quad \forall_{t,b} \quad (6)$$

$$(p_{com,e})_{t,b} = (p_{com,elc})_{t,b} + (p_{com,heat})_{t,b} + (p_{com,cool})_{t,b}, \quad \forall_{t,b} \quad (7)$$

The scaling process that follows equations (1) – (7) is shown graphically in Figure 14. It is important to scale the residential values and distribute the total energy over the year first, instead of, for example, normalizing the NREL data for each of electricity, heat, and cooling and applying the scaling factor to each of these profiles. This would make the assumption that each sector's share of total energy consumption would be the same.

Figure 14: Flowchart to Obtain Commercial Loads

The system aggregated commercial load for each end-use fuel is displayed in Figure 15. All commercial loads in the model follow the same NREL building load profile, that being of a hospital.

Figure 15: System Level Commercial Load

Industrial Loads

Much like the commercial loads, industrial loads can not be directly calculated using the NREL dataset, due to missing data on total industrial floor space. Instead, the same process applied to the commercial loads, using equations (1) – (6) and Figure 14, to estimate industrial loads. However, the NREL dataset does not provide loads industrial buildings (ie. factories, manufacturing plants, ect...), therefore, a large hotel's load profile is used to approximate industrial loads.

Due to industrial loads having a significant amount of heating demand, these load types are heavily reliant on the gas network to deliver heat through furnaces or similar technologies. On Vancouver Island, not all buses are connected to the natural gas network (see Figure 5). In these cases, the required power-to-heat capacity (ie. heat pumps) will be overstated as in reality these locations will have minimal industrial loads. To compensate for this, all buses that are not connected to the gas network have their industrial loads reduced by 90%. Ninety percent is chosen as according to the Energy Information Administration at [41] approximately 10 – 15% of industrial load is met through electricity or renewables. Therefore, we assume our system should be able to comfortably meet this amount through the electricity network. Figure 16 shows the system industrial load broken down by end-use fuel.

Figure 16: System Level Industrial Load

Electric Vehicle Loads

The NREL dataset at [37] does not include electric vehicle (EV) demand in its building system models, however, with electric vehicle adoption rates increasing it is important to account for this increasing electrical load. The NREL has published the Electric Vehicle Infrastructure – Projection Tool (EVI-Pro) [42] to estimate electric vehicle infrastructure requirements in United States cities and regions. A simplified web-based version of the NREL EVI-Pro tool at [43] provides estimates on EV load profiles by charging type and day of the week (weekday or weekend). Using this data, an average load profile at a per car level can be calculated.

The Insurance Corporation of British Columbia (ICBC) publishes vehicle registration rates for BC at [44]. This database can be filtered by vehicle type and by geographic location to find the total number of vehicles (hybrid, EV, or other) on Vancouver Island. For this study, only light-duty passenger vehicles are considered. Combining the per vehicle load profile from the NREL, and number of EVs registered on Vancouver Island from ICBC, a total EV load can be calculated and evenly distributed throughout the island. The system EV load profile for a week is shown in Figure 17, with each week in the year having the same profile. Of note in Figure 17 are the second and third days having different profiles when compared to the other days, representing weekends versus weekdays. While the load is currently quite small, in scenarios we investigate higher electrification rates.

Figure 17: System Level Electric Vehicle Load

Total System Load

Figure 18a shows the total system load broken down by sector, while Figure 18b shows the distribution of the energy load. As expected, industrial loads account for the largest share of the total system load, and energy loads are located near population centers with the largest energy transmission capacities, such as in Victoria in the south.

(a)

(b)

Figure 18: System Load by (a) Sector (b) Location

Data Validation

While the actual loads on Vancouver Island are not expected to match the modelled loads, we expect them to be on the same order of magnitude. To validate this, we use total system load data provided openly by BC Hydro at [36]. Using simple population distributions, through finding the percentage of BC's population living on Vancouver Island, we can approximate actual load on the island. Using only population will have its own errors, such as not factoring in industrial load centers, however, this is a reasonable check to see if we are on the same order of magnitudes.

Table 3 highlights the estimated absolute errors in comparing the approximated actual load to our modelled load. Notably, the mean and median error are ~60%. While this is a large error, our errors are relatively consistent and are not outside the realm of possibility for what a system of this size can expect. Obtaining more detailed load data is discussed in the future work section.

Table 3: Approximated Load Errors

Statistic	Value
Count	8758
Mean Error	57.4 %
Minimum Error	8.2 %
25% Quartile	52.6 %
Median Error	59.9 %
75% Quartile	64.9 %
Maximum Error	72.0 %

Linking to CCHP Model

An optimization model of a single CCHP system has been created in [x] and is linked to our model. While [x] has full details on the optimization, to summarize, it optimizes the capacity and generation for a CCHP system for a given power, heat and cooling load over a series of different days. The goal of linking the CCHP model to our model is to understand the benefits detailed CCHP systems can have on linking the gas and electrical grids to meet increasing electrification loads without creating excessive emissions.

The demand in the CCHP optimization model is based on the same NREL OpenEI dataset used in our model [37], specifically following the demand for a hospital load. Therefore, since we use the same hospital load profile to model our commercial load, we can transfer the capacity and generation results into our model. While the load profiles in the models will be the same, the magnitudes will be different. Therefore, we scale results from the CCHP optimization to meet our values. We use CCHPs to meet all commercial load in our model and do not allow any further investment.

Results from the CCHP optimization model provide natural gas usage rates and the amount of excess electricity needed by the system for each timestep. To translate these results into our model, we replace all commercial electrical, heating, and cooling demand with a single gas demand from the CCHP optimization, as shown in Figure 20. Any excess electricity the CCHP system needs is represented by a new electrical load. This is done as the CCHP optimization results return a non-linear function which can not be directly added to our linear optimization model. The CCHP capacity is translated into the model for

visualization purposes, however, it can not generate energy as its demand is now represented by a gas demand.

Figure 19: (a) Model Setup to Freely Allow CCHP Systems to Generate Energy and Meet End-Use Demand (b) Result of Translating CCHP Optimization Results into our Model. CCHP System can not Generate Energy and all Commercial End-Use demand is Translated into a Gas Demand

Hydrogen Blending

Modelling the blending of hydrogen into the natural gas network can quickly become complex, as ensuring a consistent blending ratio at the system level is difficult without including electrolyzers at all buses. As this study focuses on the capacity requirements and emission reduction potential of using excess electricity to produce hydrogen, rather than the difficulties of operating such as system, a simpler blending approach is taken.

To generate hydrogen, a wind farm is added in a location with an above average capacity factor (see Figure 20a). The wind farm is then connected to an on-site electrolyser, to convert electricity to hydrogen, from which it is connected via a pipeline to the only natural gas intake for the island (see Figure 20b). While building a pipeline to accommodate this is likely impractical, this assumption allows us to understand capacity requirements to generate the desired hydrogen blends. Moreover, by performing the blending at the gas intake location, we guarantee the entirety of the gas network will have the same hydrogen blend.

Figure 20: (a) Average Yearly Capacity Factor of Dedicated Hydrogen Wind Farm Location, and (b) Schematic of modelled Hydrogen and Gas Blending Process

The blending requirements follow equations (8) through (10). The upper and lower blending mixtures (expressed as a decimal) are given by h_u and h_l respectively, while the energy generation from the electrolyzer and natural gas generator are given by g_{h2} and g_{ng} respectively. The electrolyzer has an efficiency of 80% [45] applied for all timeslices. The blending requirements are based on volumetric mixtures, due to the CCHP model being based on this blending method. g_{h2} and g_{ng} are converted from energy to volumes through the constants V_h and V_{ng} found at [46].

$$h_l \leq h_u \quad (8)$$

$$(g_{h2})_t \times V_h - (g_{ng})_t \times h_l \times V_{ng} \geq 0, \quad \forall_t \quad (9)$$

$$(g_{ng})_t \times h_u \times V_{ng} - (g_{h2})_t \times V_h \geq 0, \quad \forall_t \quad (10)$$

It is important to note this equation is satisfied for all time slices, and not over multiple time slices (such as over a day). Therefore, if there are periods of low wind generation, the model's ability to generate new gas will be diminished as hydrogen can not be generated without building excessive amounts of wind capacity.

Scenarios

Eighteen scenarios are run in this study to capture the effects CCHP systems, hydrogen blending, and EV electrification rates will have on the system. The matrix of scenarios, with corresponding scenario names, is presented in Table 4.

Table 4: Scenario Matrix

CCHP System	No			Yes		
Hydrogen Blend (%)	0	20	50	0	20	50
EV Electrification						
Current (~3%)	Baseline	20H2	50H2	CCHP	CCHP-20H2	CCHP-50H2
50 %	50EV	20H2-50EV	50H2-50EV	CCHP-50EV	CCHP-20H2-50EV	CCHP-50H2-50EV
100 %	100EV	20H2-100EV	50H2-100EV	CCHP-100EV	CCHP-20H2-100EV	CCHP-50H2-100EV

The scenarios describe three different technology pathways, the adoption of widespread CCHP systems, the use of hydrogen to reduce emissions, and increased EV penetration rates. The hydrogen blend percentages are based on current blend amounts (0%), estimates on what a feasible blending amount would be with current infrastructure (20%), and what an extreme blending amount would be (50%). For the hydrogen blending scenarios, a $\pm 2\%$ leeway is given on the blend amount, for example, in the 20% scenario, the blend amount will be held between 18% and 22%. In the 50% blend scenario, the CCHP results from a 30% blend is used due to model restrictions. Finally, EV electrification rates are based on CleanBC's 2030 Roadmap [47] which states that all vehicle sales in the province must be zero-emission by the year 2030. In this scenario, we are not forecasting to estimate the number of cars on the road by 2030, instead, we look at the results of electrifying 50% and 100% of the current fleet.

Each scenario is run sequentially over 5 unique days, selected by clustering demand data discussed in [x]. These days are March 19th, June 19th, September 9th, September 13th, and December 7th, with each day having $96 \times 15min$ intervals, resulting in 480 time steps over the model horizon. All scenarios are run using the Gurobi Optimizer [48] on a Core-i9 9900 workstation with 64GB of memory.

General assumptions applied to all scenarios include a carbon tax of $\frac{\$20}{T CO2}$, importing electricity from the mainland has no emissions, the cost of installing the electrolyzer, associated wind farm, and hydrogen transmission line are not considered (due to not accounting for amortization), and the starting and ending pressures of all gas pipeline stores over the model horizon must be the same.

Results and Discussion

With no CCHP system, no hydrogen blending, and current EV rates (our baseline scenario) the system imports significant amounts of power from mainland British Columbia each day, as shown in Figure 21. In addition to the significant energy imports, the system consistently runs hydroelectric power and natural gas generation at or near max capacity. Furnaces are favored as the main method to generate heat (especially evident in days 1 and 4), and variable renewables (run-of-river and wind farms) only contribute meaningful amounts to the total generation on days 3 and 5.

The inability to generate enough electricity to supply its own demand, resulting in large amounts of imports, is perhaps the biggest take away from the reference scenario. This not only shows how immediate of an issue additional electrical load will be, but also allows for a clear demonstration of the effects integrating the gas and electrical grid will have of offsetting demand on the electrical system.

Figure 22 compares the generation mix for the fifth day (December 7th) across three different scenarios; our baseline scenario, a high hydrogen blend scenario (50H2), and a high hydrogen blend and EV penetration scenario (50H2 – 100EV). The heat demand is quite high on December 7th, which results in a large usage of furnaces as shown in plot (a). We see furnaces being prioritized over heat pumps due to the need of the system to import expensive electricity from the mainland. This coupled with the fact that the system has natural gas stored in the pipeline, the gas imports are below the maximum allowed, and costs for natural gas are lower than that of electricity, make furnaces the cheaper option.

Imposing the hydrogen blending constraint, as shown in plot (b), showcases the amount of wind generation needed to maintain the blend, and that heat pumps are now contributing to the heat demand. Heat pumps are being used to offload generation from furnaces and let storage within the pipelines gradually recharge for periods of later use. This is opposed to plot (a) where the network can simply

recharge through importing more gas without needing to worry about wind generation. Due to our assumption that for every timeslice the blending constraints (equations (9) and (10)) need to be satisfied, restricts when gas can be imported. However, once electrical demand surpasses supply (~11:30am) electricity is imported again and model switches back to a furnace only system, due to the high cost of importing electricity. While this scenario shows a better interplay of furnaces and heat pumps, it comes at the cost of installing nearly 1GW of wind turbines and an accompanying electrolyzer capacity.

The inability of Vancouver Island to meet its own electrical supply and resorting to carbon emitting furnaces is even more clear in Figure 22(c). With increased electrical demand due to high EV penetration, the island now needs to import even more electricity. This results in a lower utilization rate of heat pumps due to the higher cost of electricity. The charging of the pipeline is then compensated by charging the pipelines to higher pressures during the preceding days to account for the time of needing to import electricity (9:00am onwards). If these systems have a method to generate electricity through the use of gas, we expect the results to show less electricity imports and a greater interplay between furnaces and heat pumps.

Figure 21: Generation Mix of Reference Scenario, with the Black Load Line Representing Total Energy Load (Electricity, Heating, and Cooling)

(a)

(b)

(c)

Figure 22: December 8th Generation with the Black Load Line Representing Total Energy Load (Electricity, Heating, and Cooling) for (a) Reference Scenario (b) Reference with 50% Hydrogen Blend (c) Reference with 50% Hydrogen Blend and 100% EV

Implementing a CCHP system in our baseline scenario (CCHP scenario) and rerunning the model produces results in Figure 23. Two key findings are immediately visible; heat pumps are used to replace some of the heat demand that was initially met by furnaces, and the amount of electricity the system is importing is reduced (see Table 5). The primary driver of these changes is that the system can now cheaply make electricity through CCHP systems. As shown by days 1 and 5 in Figure 23, during the morning hours heat pumps are used in part due to the extra electricity CCHP systems are providing. However, this does not get around the fact that there are still consistently periods of electricity shortages on the island. During all days, electricity is being imported while CCHP systems are also generating electricity. This deficit is made even clearer in high EV penetration scenarios (see Table 5).

Figure 24 compares the generation mix for the fifth day (December 7th) across three different CCHP scenarios; our baseline scenario with CCHP, a high hydrogen blend scenario (*CCHP – 50H2*), and a high hydrogen blend and EV penetration scenario (*CCHP – 50H2 – 100EV*). In the baseline scenario we see consistent electrical generation from the CCHP system, and two periods of heat demand being shared by heat pumps and furnaces; these are times where there is excess electrical generation capacity in the system. This is an extremely important finding; providing the system a method to generate electricity from the gas network results in less imported electricity.

Unlike our scenarios without CCHPs, adding a hydrogen blend does not significantly change how heat demand is being met. Since the system already uses gas to generate heat and electricity through CCHPs, which offsets the periods of electricity shortfalls, there is no need for the system to increase heat pump usage. However, if electricity demand increase, as shown in Figure 24c, electricity is imported to make up for any shortfalls, at which point the model resorts to using the cheapest option to generate heat (furnaces) as all imported electricity is used to meet end use demand.

While this behaviour allows us to draw conclusions about the impact CCHP system can have on the generation mix, it is important to remember that all CCHP capacity and generation is exogenously defined to only meet commercial load. If CCHP capacity investments are endogenously made, we could see a greater switch to the technology as there is clearly a need to generate electricity through other means than the existing infrastructure on the island. However, maximum install limits would need to be set at a per industry level (residential, commercial, industrial). For example, the economics of installing a CCHP system for every detached residential home is likely not feasible. Therefore, either limiting CCHP investment and/or adding more sector coupling technologies to the model (such as only combined heat and power) can give further insight on transition pathways.

Figure 23: Generation Mix of Reference Scenario Plus CCHP System, with the Black Load Line Representing Total Energy Load (Electricity, Heating, and Cooling)

(a)

(b)

(c)

Figure 24: December 7th Generation Mix, with the Black Load Line Representing Total Energy Load (Electricity, Heating, and Cooling) for (a) Reference Scenario with CCHP (b) Reference with 50% Hydrogen Blend and CCHP and (c) Reference with 50% Hydrogen Blend and 100% EV and CCHP

Investigating the generation mix gives us insight on the operational characteristics of the system, however, studying system level cost and emission metrics is also useful to determine the feasibility of implementing such a system.

Table 6 shows the normalized system cost between all 18 scenarios. As EV demand increases, the system costs becomes more expensive due to increasing amounts of expensive electricity imports. However, the more interesting result is minimal system cost differences between the hydrogen blending scenarios. While encouraging, this is only showing operational savings, as the capital costs of installing the wind farm and electrolyzer are not accounted for in the hydrogen blending scenarios. A long-term model needs to be developed to account for capital investment decisions and determine the true cost of the system. Finally, through the implementation of CCHP systems, the system cost is lowered which is again driven by the expensive electricity being imported in the non-CCHP systems.

Table 6: Normalized System Level Costs (Green is Cheaper)

CCHP System	No			Yes		
Hydrogen Blend (%)	0	20	50	0	20	50
EV Electrification						
Current (~3%)	0.42	0.42	0.42	0.30	0.29	0.29
50 %	0.70	0.70	0.70	0.57	0.56	0.56
100 %	1.00	1.00	1.00	0.86	0.85	0.85

Table 7 shows the normalized system level emissions across all 18 scenarios. The actual magnitudes of the values are not included due to various modelling assumptions; such as importing electricity having no emissions and the exclusion of non-EV transportation emissions. As expected, switching to a CCHP system increases the total emissions due to higher gas usage. However, the more interesting results is looking at Table 6 and Table 7 together. While the operational costs of the system remain relatively stable across hydrogen blending scenarios, emissions decrease. This highlights a key finding; through the use of CCHP systems we can obtain a cheaper system, and coupling this with hydrogen blending we can manage emissions at no extra cost. This does however come with the caveat that to reduce emissions (and head towards net-zero) we will need to be blending in more than 20% hydrogen into the natural gas supply. However, in literature, 15 – 20% is often cited as the maximum amount if the goal is to use existing infrastructure.

Table 7: Normalized System Level Emissions (Green is Less Emissions)

CCHP System	No			Yes		
Hydrogen Blend (%)	0	20	50	0	20	50
EV Electrification						
Current (~3%)	0.67	0.56	0.38	0.96	0.77	0.51
50 %	0.70	0.57	0.39	0.98	0.80	0.53
100 %	0.71	0.58	0.40	1.00	0.81	0.54

Conclusion

In this study we build a sector coupled PyPSA model of Vancouver Island to investigate the effects of linking the electrical and gas grids through the use of hydrogen blending and CCHP systems. GIS infrastructure data is collected to model the networks, while census data coupled with open-source NREL datasets are used to estimate residential, commercial, industrial, and electric vehicle demand. A combined cooling, heat, and power system (CCHP) optimization study is linked to our model to provide insight on capacity and generation potential at various hydrogen mixtures. Weather datasets are utilized to estimate wind and run-of-river generation potential for each unique time slice. The model is run at 15min intervals over a series of 5 days selected based on clustering demand profiles over the year. Results from the model show the generation mix of the system to meet end use electrical, heating, and cooling demands. Moreover, system costs and emissions are tracked and reported.

Our research shows that implementing CCHP systems in the Vancouver Island network will result in a cheaper system to operate, however, at the expense of increasing emissions. The emission increase is primarily caused by the island switching from importing expensive, emission free, electricity to generating cheap electricity via CCHPs. Furthermore, though blending hydrogen into the system, system costs remain steady while emissions decrease. This highlights that a system with CCHPs and a high hydrogen blend can result in a cheaper and less emitting system. However, this does come at the cost of needing roughly 1GW of wind capacity to manage blending ratios. Finally, with further electric vehicle penetration, the island's inability to internally meet its own electrical demand results in increasing reliance on importing electricity due to capacity limitations on its own gas infrastructure.

Results from this study are useful to evaluate different decarbonization pathways by integrating the natural gas and electrical networks, however, the model can only be used as a case study and needs further work to inform British Columbia policy. Three future development pathways are clearly visible and are next discussed; the first is in relation to the input data, the second is in relation to the modelling assumptions, and the third is in the linking of the CCHP system.

Future Work

Model results are only as good as our input data, and specifically our load approximation methods are simply estimates and do not necessarily reflect the actual loads on Vancouver Island. For example, using a single profile to model all our commercial load (and similarly with our industrial load) will likely create artifacts in the system that are not normally seen. Moreover, through using the national averages to scale loads, we are assuming commercial and industrial loads are evenly distributed throughout the island. However, in reality there are often specific locations where these loads will be grouped, such as at pulp mills. Contacting BC Hydro to gain access to substation level residential, commercial, and industrial load data is required to present effective policy feedback.

Further expanding on the validation of our input data is performing a larger range of sensitivity tests. For example, the clustering algorithm used to choose the 5 representative days in the study are based on the demand profiles. While this may be suitable, other factors such as the hourly wind capacity factors or run-of-river generation can be added to the clustering algorithm to select better representative days. Moreover, the impact run-of-river generation profiles have on system results needs to be further tested. With many run-of-river stations scattered around the island, they can help meet loads in more rural areas. However, without knowing the specific flow rates and turbines associated with each station, the

generation profiles can only be loosely estimated. Either collecting this data or performing sensitivity tests on these parameters will help validate the system.

Modelling assumptions relate to how the constraints you impose on the model affects its operation. The larger assumptions in our model that deserve further research are the hydrogen blending methods, storage assumptions associated with gas pipelines, and the exclusion of other storage mediums. As described in Figure 20b, we model hydrogen blending to occur at the natural gas intake to the island which ensures consistent blending ratios. In reality, blending will likely happen at different locations within the gas network. Capturing these blending methods can better represent the impact of hydrogen, as the ratio between natural gas and hydrogen in the system will likely float. Moreover, we constrain the system to force the hydrogen and natural gas blend ratio at all timesteps, rather than over a period of timesteps. This brings the intermittency issue of variable renewables back into our problem, as if wind is not generating then we can not import gas onto the island. Further investigation on how hydrogen blending is done at a system scale, how to implement these constraints, and how this will affect system behaviour is needed.

Proper modelling of storage in energy models are a widely discussed topic in the literature, however, most research points to the significance storage will have on our energy system. As an operational model, we did not consider storage options other than gas pipelines due to no storage infrastructure currently existing. This will likely change in the near future and planning for storage integration is needed. Moreover, testing storage assumptions on the gas pipelines, such as the storage levels at the start and end of the model horizon being the same, should be done to test the stability of our results.

Finally, using the outputs of the CCHP optimization to build custom constraints into a linear program can be investigated. In this study, we directly took the CCHP optimization results and exogenously altered our demand. While effective, this method is not scalable to other demand profiles. Creating a link that models a linear response surface model from a CCHP optimization as a piecewise function will give the model improved flexibility on when and how to use CCHP systems.

References

- [1] S. Canada, "UN conference on climate action: COP26 in Glasgow," Oct. 19, 2021. <https://www.canada.ca/en/services/environment/weather/climatechange/canada-international-action/un-climate-change-conference/cop26-summit.html> (accessed Nov. 20, 2021).
- [2] G. Jayadev, B. D. Leibowicz, and E. Kutanoglu, "U.S. electricity infrastructure of the future: Generation and transmission pathways through 2050," *Appl. Energy*, vol. 260, p. 114267, Feb. 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.apenergy.2019.114267.
- [3] S. Motalebi, T. Barnes, L. Lu, B. D. Leibowicz, and T. Niet, "The role of U.S.-Canada electricity trade in North American decarbonization pathways," *Energy Strategy Rev.*, vol. 41, p. 100827, May 2022, doi: 10.1016/j.esr.2022.100827.
- [4] A. Mahone *et al.*, "On the Path to Decarbonization: Electrification and Renewables in California and the Northeast United States," *IEEE Power Energy Mag.*, vol. 16, no. 4, pp. 58–68, Jul. 2018, doi: 10.1109/MPE.2018.2822865.
- [5] T. Brown, M. Schäfer, and M. Greiner, "Sectoral Interactions as Carbon Dioxide Emissions Approach Zero in a Highly-Renewable European Energy System," *Energies*, vol. 12, no. 6, Art. no. 6, Jan. 2019, doi: 10.3390/en12061032.
- [6] S. Evangelopoulou, A. De Vita, G. Zazias, and P. Capros, "Energy System Modelling of Carbon-Neutral Hydrogen as an Enabler of Sectoral Integration within a Decarbonization Pathway," *Energies*, vol. 12, no. 13, Art. no. 13, Jan. 2019, doi: 10.3390/en12132551.
- [7] M. Chaudry, N. Jenkins, M. Qadrdan, and J. Wu, "Combined gas and electricity network expansion planning," *Appl. Energy*, vol. 113, pp. 1171–1187, Jan. 2014, doi: 10.1016/j.apenergy.2013.08.071.
- [8] J. B. Nunes, N. Mahmoudi, T. K. Saha, and D. Chattopadhyay, "A stochastic integrated planning of electricity and natural gas networks for Queensland, Australia considering high renewable penetration," *Energy*, vol. 153, pp. 539–553, Jun. 2018, doi: 10.1016/j.energy.2018.03.116.
- [9] S. Clegg and P. Mancarella, "Integrated Modeling and Assessment of the Operational Impact of Power-to-Gas (P2G) on Electrical and Gas Transmission Networks," *IEEE Trans. Sustain. Energy*, vol. 6, pp. 1–11, Oct. 2015, doi: 10.1109/TSTE.2015.2424885.
- [10] A. Herbst, F. Toro, F. Reitze, and E. Jochem, "Introduction to Energy Systems Modelling," *Swiss J. Econ. Stat.*, vol. 148, no. 2, Art. no. 2, Apr. 2012, doi: 10.1007/BF03399363.
- [11] J. Bistline, G. Blanford, T. Mai, and J. Merrick, "Modeling variable renewable energy and storage in the power sector," *Energy Policy*, vol. 156, p. 112424, Sep. 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.enpol.2021.112424.
- [12] B. Shirizadeh and P. Quirion, "Do multi-sector energy system optimization models need hourly temporal resolution? A case study with an investment and dispatch model applied to France," *Appl. Energy*, vol. 305, p. 117951, Jan. 2022, doi: 10.1016/j.apenergy.2021.117951.
- [13] B. Nastasi, S. Mazzoni, D. Groppi, A. Romagnoli, and D. Astiaso Garcia, "Solar power-to-gas application to an island energy system," *Renew. Energy*, vol. 164, pp. 1005–1016, Feb. 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.renene.2020.10.055.
- [14] A. Maroufmashat and M. Fowler, "Transition of Future Energy System Infrastructure; through Power-to-Gas Pathways," *Energies*, vol. 10, no. 8, Art. no. 8, Aug. 2017, doi: 10.3390/en10081089.
- [15] W. Gu *et al.*, "Modeling, planning and optimal energy management of combined cooling, heating and power microgrid: A review," *Int. J. Electr. Power Energy Syst.*, vol. 54, pp. 26–37, Jan. 2014, doi: 10.1016/j.ijepes.2013.06.028.
- [16] M. Wegener *et al.*, "A techno-economic optimization model of a biomass-based CCHP/heat pump system under evolving climate conditions," *Energy Convers. Manag.*, vol. 223, p. 113256, Nov. 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.enconman.2020.113256.

- [17] S. Soheyli, M. H. Shafiei Mayam, and M. Mehrjoo, "Modeling a novel CCHP system including solar and wind renewable energy resources and sizing by a CC-MOPSO algorithm," *Appl. Energy*, vol. 184, pp. 375–395, Dec. 2016, doi: 10.1016/j.apenergy.2016.09.110.
- [18] N. Li, X. Zhao, X. Shi, Z. Pei, H. Mu, and F. Taghizadeh-Hesary, "Integrated energy systems with CCHP and hydrogen supply: A new outlet for curtailed wind power," *Appl. Energy*, vol. 303, p. 117619, Dec. 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.apenergy.2021.117619.
- [19] T. Brown, J. Hörsch, and D. Schlachtberger, "PyPSA: Python for Power System Analysis," *J. Open Res. Softw.*, vol. 6, no. 1, Art. no. 1, Jan. 2018, doi: 10.5334/jors.188.
- [20] T. Brown, D. Schlachtberger, A. Kies, S. Schramm, and M. Greiner, "Synergies of sector coupling and transmission reinforcement in a cost-optimised, highly renewable European energy system," *Energy*, vol. 160, pp. 720–739, Oct. 2018, doi: 10.1016/j.energy.2018.06.222.
- [21] M. Victoria, K. Zhu, T. Brown, G. B. Andresen, and M. Greiner, "The role of storage technologies throughout the decarbonisation of the sector-coupled European energy system," *Energy Convers. Manag.*, vol. 201, p. 111977, Dec. 2019, doi: 10.1016/j.enconman.2019.111977.
- [22] Integrated Cadastral Information Society and BCGOV ILMB Crown Registry and Geographic Base Branch, "Integrated Cadastral Information Society (ICIS)." Abacus Data Network, 2015. [Online]. Available: <https://hdl.handle.net/11272.1/AB2/4C5NWR>
- [23] L. L. Grigsby, *Electric Power Generation, Transmission, and Distribution: The Electric Power Engineering Handbook*, 3rd ed. CRC Press, 2018. doi: 10.1201/9781315222424.
- [24] "BC Hydro Operating Order 5T-14." Accessed: Dec. 05, 2021. [Online]. Available: https://www.bchydro.com/content/dam/BCHydro/customer-portal/documents/corporate/suppliers/transmission-system/system_operating_orders/5T-14.pdf
- [25] N. R. Canada, "Natural Gas: A Primer," Jan. 18, 2011. <https://www.nrcan.gc.ca/energy/energy-sources-distribution/natural-gas/natural-gas-primer/5641> (accessed Jul. 23, 2022).
- [26] "BC Hydro Generation System." <https://www.bchydro.com/energy-in-bc/operations/generation.html> (accessed Jul. 23, 2022).
- [27] "BC Hydro Independent Projects." <https://www.bchydro.com/work-with-us/selling-clean-energy/meeting-energy-needs/how-power-is-acquired.html> (accessed Jul. 23, 2022).
- [28] J. Kiviluoma and P. Meibom, "Influence of wind power, plug-in electric vehicles, and heat storages on power system investments," *Energy*, vol. 35, no. 3, pp. 1244–1255, Mar. 2010, doi: 10.1016/j.energy.2009.11.004.
- [29] L. Vimmerstedt *et al.*, "2022 Annual Technology Baseline (ATB) Cost and Performance Data for Electricity Generation Technologies." DOE Open Energy Data Initiative (OEDI); National Renewable Energy Laboratory (NREL), p. 8 files, 2022. doi: 10.25984/1871952.
- [30] "Natural gas rates - residential," www.fortisbc.com. <https://www.fortisbc.com/accounts-billing/billing-rates/natural-gas-rates/residential-rates> (accessed Jul. 24, 2022).
- [31] O. US EPA, "GHG Emission Factors Hub," Jul. 27, 2015. <https://www.epa.gov/climateleadership/ghg-emission-factors-hub> (accessed May 26, 2022).
- [32] F. Hofmann, J. Hampp, F. Neumann, T. Brown, and J. Hörsch, "atlite: A Lightweight Python Package for Calculating Renewable Power Potentials and Time Series," *J. Open Source Softw.*, vol. 6, no. 62, p. 3294, Jun. 2021, doi: 10.21105/joss.03294.
- [33] H. Hersbach *et al.*, "ERA5 hourly data on single levels from 1959 to present." Copernicus Climate Change Service (C3S) Climate Data Store (CDS), 2018. [Online]. Available: 10.24381/cds.adbb2d47
- [34] B. Lehner and G. Grill, "Global river hydrography and network routing: baseline data and new approaches to study the world's large river systems: GLOBAL RIVER HYDROGRAPHY AND NETWORK ROUTING," *Hydrol. Process.*, vol. 27, no. 15, pp. 2171–2186, Jul. 2013, doi: 10.1002/hyp.9740.
- [35] "HydroBASINS." <https://www.hydrosheds.org/products/hydrobasins> (accessed Jul. 24, 2022).

- [36] "BC Hydro Historical Flow Data." <https://www.bchydro.com/energy-in-bc/operations/transmission/transmission-system/actual-flow-data/historical-data.html> (accessed Jul. 24, 2022).
- [37] E. Wilson *et al.*, "End-Use Load Profiles for the U.S. Building Stock." DOE Open Energy Data Initiative (OEDI); National Renewable Energy Laboratory (NREL), p. 7 files, 2021. doi: 10.25984/1876417.
- [38] E. Wilson *et al.*, "End-Use Load Profiles for the U.S. Building Stock: Methodology and Results of Model Calibration, Validation, and Uncertainty Quantification," NREL/TP-5500-80889, 1854582, MainId:78667, Mar. 2022. doi: 10.2172/1854582.
- [39] Statistics Canada, "Population and dwelling counts: Canada and census divisions." Statistics Canada, 2022. [Online]. Available: <https://www12.statcan.gc.ca/census-recensement/2021/dp-pd/hlt-fst/pd-pl/index-eng.cfm>
- [40] CER, "Canada's Energy Future Data Appendices." Canada Energy Regulator, 2016. doi: 10.35002/ZJR8-8X75.
- [41] "Use of energy in industry - U.S. Energy Information Administration (EIA)." <https://www.eia.gov/energyexplained/use-of-energy/industry.php> (accessed Jul. 24, 2022).
- [42] D.-Y. Lee, N. Reinicke, E. Wood, Y. Ge, and E. Burrell, "Electric Vehicle Infrastructure Projection Tool (EVI-Pro)," National Renewable Energy Lab. (NREL), Golden, CO (United States), NREL/PR-5400-77651, Jan. 2021. Accessed: Jul. 24, 2022. [Online]. Available: <https://www.osti.gov/biblio/1764904>
- [43] NREL, "Alternative Fuels Data Center: Electric Vehicle Infrastructure Projection Tool (EVI-Pro) Lite." <https://afdc.energy.gov/evi-pro-lite/load-profile> (accessed Jul. 24, 2022).
- [44] Insurance Corporation of British Columbia, "Vehicle Insurance Policies in Force," *Tableau Public*. <https://public.tableau.com/app/profile/icbc/viz/QuickStatistics-Policiesinforce/VehicleInsurancePoliciesinForce> (accessed Jul. 24, 2022).
- [45] S. Shiva Kumar and V. Himabindu, "Hydrogen production by PEM water electrolysis – A review," *Mater. Sci. Energy Technol.*, vol. 2, no. 3, pp. 442–454, Dec. 2019, doi: 10.1016/j.mset.2019.03.002.
- [46] U. Bossel and B. Eliasson, "Energy and the Hydrogen Economy," p. 36.
- [47] "CleanBC 2030 Roadmap." Accessed: Jul. 29, 2022. [Online]. Available: https://www2.gov.bc.ca/assets/gov/environment/climate-change/action/cleanbc/cleanbc_roadmap_2030.pdf
- [48] "Gurobi Optimizer Reference Manual." 2022. [Online]. Available: <https://www.gurobi.com>